

3-(*p*-Dimethylamino)Anilino-methyl Salicylic Acid Hydrazide as a Chelating Agent for the Gravimetric Determination of Zirconium(IV)

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A new tetradentate salicylic acid hydrazide base 3-(*p*-dimethylamino)anilino-methyl salicylic acid hydrazide (DAMSH) has been synthesized and characterised by ir and elemental analyses. This ligand has been used as a chelating agent for the gravimetric determination of Zr(IV). The metal ligand complexation ratio has been found to be 1 : 1. IR spectra of the chelate show that the metal is coordinated with C=O, hydrazinic -NH₂, -OH and -NH group of the base.

A number of reagents have been attempted¹⁻⁹ for the gravimetric estimation of zirconium. Extensive search of literature reveals that no work has been done with salicylic acid hydrazide-Mannich base complexes of Zr(IV).

In the present studies, a new tetradentate ligand, 3-(*p*-dimethyl amino)anilino-methyl salicylic acid hydrazide (DAMSH), has been synthesized, characterised by elemental analysis and ir spectra and has been used for the gravimetric determination of Zr(IV) in Zr(IV) salts.

DAMSH has proved to be a better reagent for gravimetric determination of Zr over the previously known procedures because very small quantities (5-8 mg) of Zr may be estimated with this reagent even when present in its ore. Moreover, the precipitate is quantitative and crystalline.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Anhydrous ZrOCl₂ was prepared as reported¹⁰. Dioxane used was purified by the usual method¹¹. The metal content of the chelate was determined as reported¹².

Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer, model 521 and Beckmann IR-12 were used for recording the ir spectra of the ligand and the chelate.

Preparation of the reagent :

Salicylic acid hydrazide was prepared by the action of hydrazine hydrate on ethyl salicylate. *p*-Dimethyl amino aniline was prepared from *p*-nitroso dimethyl aniline, the latter being obtained from dimethyl aniline¹³. The reagent was prepared by condensing salicylic acid hydrazide (in dioxane), the amine and formaldehyde according to the reported conditions¹⁴. The reagent was characterised by its ir spectrum, elemental analysis and m.p. 204°.

The reagent was used in the form of a 10% solution in dioxane.

Gravimetric determination of zirconium :

A standard Zr(IV) solution was prepared by dissolving a known weight of zirconyl chloride in 0.1 N HCl and standardised gravimetrically as ZrO₂ by N-benzoyl phenyl hydroxylamine¹⁵⁻¹⁶.

Procedure :

An aliquot of the standard zirconium solution was taken in a beaker and diluted to 150-160 ml. pH of the solution was adjusted to 3.8-3.9 by adding appropriate quantity of a solution of ammonium acetate. A hot solution of the organic reagent was added with continuous stirring. The light yellow precipitate formed was digested on water bath for ~0.5 hr at 80°. The precipitate was filtered after cooling and washed with an excess of a hot solution of the organic reagent, dried, ignited and weighed as ZrO₂. The data showing the amounts of ZrO₂ taken and found on analysis are given in Table I.

TABLE I—DETERMINATION OF Zr(IV)

ZrO ₂		Error (%)
Taken (mg)	Found (mg)	
6.40	6.39	-0.16
6.80	6.81	-0.15
5.20	5.21	+0.19
7.80	7.79	-0.15
8.00	8.00	0.00
8.20	8.21	+0.12

Results and Discussion

The results obtained are in good agreement with those obtained using N-benzoyl phenyl hydroxylamine as precipitating agent. Moreover the reagent can estimate as low as 5 mg of Zr. But serious interference was observed with Fe(III), Th(IV),

Ti(IV), V(V) and La(III). Fluoride as sodium salt caused interference. The data indicating the interference of the above ions are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF Zr(IV) IN PRESENCE OF FOREIGN IONS

Metal ion added	ZrO ₂		Error (%)
	Taken (mg)	Found (mg)	
Fe(III) 70 mg	8.00	8.80	+10.0
Th(IV) 80 mg	8.00	8.60	+ 7.5
Ti(IV) 90 mg	8.00	7.20	-10.0
V(V) 80 mg	8.00	8.60	+ 7.5
La(III) 50 mg	8.00	8.80	+10.0
F ⁻ as sodium salt 50 mg	8.00	8.72	+ 9.0

The infrared spectrum of the zirconium chelate shows the absence of absorption band characteristic for -OH (phenolic) group, indicating that this group takes part in chelation and the proton is replaced from it by metal ion during chelation. The calculation of the metal ligand stability constants confirmed the complexation ratio to be 1 : 1.

However the strong absorption band due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$, appearing in the ligand at 1650 cm^{-1} , gets shifted to lower frequency region of 1620 cm^{-1} in the chelate, indicating that C=O is involved in bond formation with the metal through the oxygen atom. The lowering of the band at 3250 cm^{-1} by 30 cm^{-1} in the metal chelate is suggestive of hydrazinic -NH₂ coordination to the metal ion. It is, however, not possible for hydrazinic NH and NH₂ groups to be simultaneously bonded but -NH group of (*p*-dimethyl amino)anilino-methyl entity of the ligand

attached at position-3 takes part in chelation with the metal ion. νNH appears at 3300 cm^{-1} in the chelate, which appeared at 3340 cm^{-1} in the ligand, indicating the coordination of -NH group to the metal through nitrogen atom. The characteristic $\nu(\text{Zr}=\text{O})$ has been observed as a weak band in the chelate at about 1020 cm^{-1} ¹⁷.

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